

Use of Information & communication technology in Higher Education & Research: Need of the day

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Article Information	Abstract
<p>Article history:</p> <p>Received: 20.02.2014 Revised: 12.03.2014 Accepted: 25.03.2014</p> <p>Keywords:</p> <p>ICT, eEducation, eLearning</p>	<p>Technology touched and changed every aspect of our life very fast, Do you realize how dramatically world has changed? Can you remember, when was the last time that you use VCR or VCD, sent a film roll to be developed, use public telephone etc. and now you think about your class room and teaching methods, are they still old as before 40-50 years?. We have the students which starts using Facebook, twitter etc. at the age of 6-7 years in their routine lifestyle, but when they enter in classroom they found themselves in age-old situation. So it is the time to think about teaching methods, it is the time to know about ICT tools and techniques useful in teaching and research. We are now living in the era of technology and evolution of internet has affected all part of life dramatically. Also the area of education has not remained untouched. Previously, student used to spend their time in library searching for information in books and journals. Now a days required information is just a click away from them, they use web search engines such as yahoo, google, MSN, Yandex, etc and figure out the web sites containing the desired information. The information sharing has become very easy due to access on World Wide Web (www) as the world persons and their knowledge attach to each other by a web and can be transferred to each other. Technology-integrated education is still a dream at all levels of education in India. Though computers are available in most of the educational institutes, however these are mostly used to learn about computers. Rarely they are used as tools for the teaching and learning of other curriculum areas. With the evolution of computer, software's and internet the traditional education tools are going to change without affecting the basic goals of education. The opportunity to use computers for teaching and learning should not be a privilege. It should be a right, just as it is only right that children should have access to books, pens and paper.</p> <p>This paper discuss how the commonly available technology resources (Computers, TV, Internet etc) of educational institutes can be used as a tool of eEducation to provide world class education and research. It also will explain how internet, computer, software and other IT based educational infrastructure are helpful to improve the quality of higher educational system including research.</p>

Introduction

In the 21st century eEducation is on the priority list of all governments, college, institutions and University. In our present traditional system of education, the teacher takes the feedback by evaluating the

students through examination or by the questions asked by the students, it consists of teacher, black board, chalk, books, students, classroom and laboratory and interaction between them. The teacher uses

this environment to create problems for student and then guides them through to experiences leading to desired learning. Here one important point is that all the components except teacher and students of an education system are dependent on technology and has evolved over the development of civilization. With the evolution of computer, software and internet traditional education and research tools are going to change without affecting the basic goals of education. Smart board, PRS, Digital Microscope, interactive pad are common tools used as a tool of eEducation.

ICTs have promised to expand the basic nature of education. Such as the ability to link written with audio and visual material that can enrich the full range of the learner's senses. The technology also creates a qualitative expansion in the means of education by taking a process rooted in the one-way delivery of knowledge and making it more participatory and reciprocal. Computer communication takes a system of learning based in narrow linear, narrative forms, and opens it up to a wide range of nonlinear, exploratory processes that allow the learner to make full use of his or her own multiple cognitive maps. The students mutually constitute their learning environments, which grow in the learning process.

Similarly the incorporation of ICTs in education and training programmes has profound influence in teaching and teacher preparation. The student accesses knowledge and information through Internet, TV, satellite and cable network and digital media to synchronize learning mediated through these multiple delivery mechanisms.

The important aspect of knowledge management is library which has changed its face in wake of the new technology. The library is the place where the information seeker can access information without restriction - the access role. The second role

has been the world-wide effort of libraries to archive, protect and provide ongoing access to information and the world's cultural heritage for the long term - the preservation role.

India has 214 universities and equivalent institutions of seven open universities. The number of students has reached the level of 6.75 million and there are 0.321m teachers in the higher education system. But the future projection suggests massive requirement of infrastructure. There is a great hope from ICTs in finding answer to the problems. ICTs provide answer to the problem and can help to take the lectures of expert educators to remote area, which did not have the required facilities or human resources.

There is another factor which has to be discussed that is the GER of the higher education of our country is 12.4. We are far behind the developed countries average of 45 per cent and even countries like China (22 per cent). The GER for Dalits, educationally backward minorities and other socially and educationally backward minorities and other socially backward classes is even lower than the national GER. The Centre has set a GER target of 30 per cent by 2020 and for this, the number of universities and colleges would have to be increased many fold, quality of existing institutions to be enhanced and existing colleges and universities will have to be expanded. On the other side EMR (educational mortality rate) whereby of 100 children enrolled in class I, not more than 26 reach class X, barely 13 qualify for higher secondary education and only 6 qualify for college education, raises serious concerns with regard to the means adopted in the teaching-learning process and of accountability which is rarely addressed. For decrease GER and EMR many factors are responsible but two major reasons are that decreasing interest of student in higher education and poor student teacher ratio.

Both problems can be solved up to a limit by using New Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) which also provide alternative provisions for access to education without compromising the achievement of comparable goals through different and more appropriate arrangements and means, enable the expansion of the scope, scale and quality of learning. The students are also able to discuss their problems with the subject expert from anywhere in the world, teachers increase their knowledge so ultimately overall impact is that UP is also able to produce best students in higher education which results in to increase employment and ultimately overall growth and development results in sectors of our state.

In paper we discuss current state of education in India. This provides a context for the ensuing discussion of the extent to which modern computer-based ICT in India are integrated into primary, secondary, and tertiary teaching and learning. Indian constitution provides the right to education for all children between the ages of 6 to 14 is defined as a constitutional right.

If a child wants to go to school, the state must provide the opportunity. But it is not obligatory on the part of parents to send their children to school. Literacy rates are thus in some states sadly low. Technology presents a ray of hope, which as yet flickers fitfully like a short-wicked candle that is struggling to burn bright. But pilot technology based projects here and there in India are showcasing the way to what could be a glowing future for a country that is already very much a power to be reckoned with amongst the community of nations.

Growth of Higher Education in India

In its size and diversity, India has the third largest higher education system in the world, next only to China and the United States. Before Independence, access to

higher education was very limited and elitist, with enrolment of less than a million students in 500 colleges and 20 universities. Since independence, the growth has been very impressive. The system is now more mass-based and democratized with one third to 40% of enrolments coming from lower socio-economic strata, and women comprising of some 35% of the total enrolments (Tilak, 2004). It is little more than half a century ever since the government initiated a planned development of higher education in the country particularly with the establishment of University Grants Commission in 1953. Thus early 1950s is an important reference points from which we could look back at our progress of higher education. Indian education system is also changing with time and start use of eEducation tools at various levels of education system in India but it require more attention from the government to keep pace with time. As early as in 1984 UGC launched countrywide classroom (CWCR) and Production facilities at 6 universities. Initially the coordination with these centers was done from UGC office with the support of a consultant. Subsequently an inter-university Centre named as 'Consortium for Educational Communication (CEC) was set up in the year 1993 for developing ICT based teaching learning programs suitable for Higher education and research. As a response target objectives the CEC coordinates the development of centers, ensuring the quality of software, coordination of telecasting of the selected films, inspiring and encouraging innovations. During the two decades of CWCR and a decade of CEC considerable progress has been made. Use of online exams system is started in our country, various online course started by Indian universities such as IGNOU.

Potential Benefit eEducation system-

- It brings a breakthrough in the education system
- It can minimise the need of subject/topic experts up to a limit by using online system.
- It change in pedagogical conceptions
- It Enabled experts of other field to be engage in higher education
- It help in the establishment of balanced education between rural and urban area
- It help teachers to aware them with the advancement of their subjects worldwide.
- It increase the attendance percent as the boring teaching replace by interesting method
- It increase the interest of student in the subject.
- It increases the enrolment of students
- It provide a variety of possibilities to deliver on campus teaching
- It provide better quality output and understanding of educational concepts through utilizing ICT
- as materials supporting class
- It provide equal higher educational opportunities which offers education at quality through the
- Internet and offers education at low cost with no limitation in time/space
- It provides an opportunity of high quality education economically, not only to the people in cities but also to those in the rural areas

Steps to be taken for Successful Technology Integration

- A non-dictatorial approach is always best
- Active support must come from the top
- Do not underestimate the on-going cost of technology- integrated teaching and learning

- Every school should have a core of teacher-computerists
- Everyone involved administration, teachers, parents and students must be committed to the ongoing change in teaching and learning methodologies that will accompany technology integration
- Parents and students must be involved in the evolutionary process
- Teachers must be given time and freedom to restructure the curriculum around the technology
- User-friendly technical support must be available, ideally onsite and on demand Teacher needs must come first

Government Initiatives in eEducation

- Fully aware the potential role of ICT in ensuring quality education to our student ensuring quality education to our student
- huge investment is being made on the huge investment is being made on the educational sector, output seems to be educational sector, output seems to be just satisfactory just satisfactory
- e-Government Master Plan of Government of India has identified e-Education as the priority Project
- The system of educational communication has grown to 17 Educational Media Research Centres and Audio Visual Research Centre, now known as Educational Multimedia Research Centres (EMMRC). Average number of educational programmes produced has increased to 1000 programmes per year from 25 in the beginning. CEC runs a 24hr higher education channel known as Vyas Channel on Gyan Darshan Bouquet now also available on DTH.

Constitutional Aspects of Indian Education

The framers of the Indian Constitution enunciated, in the Directive Principles of State Policy under Article 45, Free and Compulsory Education for all children in the age group of 6-14 years. The 73rd and 74th Constitutional amendments empowered local self-governments to manage and monitor primary education. The Supreme Court Judgment of 1993 declared education as a fundamental right, a new status in India.

Education and Five Year Plans

Since Independence, India has launched eleven five year programs. Each plan focus on for educational development, but the eleventh pan is centered on education hence commonly known as "Education Plan".

Commissions and Committees on Education

After Independence, the Government of India appointed various committees and commissions with the sole purpose of bringing about radical changes in the educational system of the country for the development of education. Here is a summary of the recommendations made. The UGC, NCERT, SCERT have provided grants to further the introduction and implementation of computer-based educational technology at all levels of education. The immediate goal is to increase access to this technology in order to improve the quality of education and to empower the people. The ultimate goal is to bring India to a place of prominence in the "global village." But, as might be expected, there are many disparities in the implementation of this directive around the country. Amongst these, the cultural, social, economic, regional disparities predominate. With regard to cultural and social disparities, for example, in some states early marriage of girls and the expectation that they will take care of the family, along with the priority given to boys education, result in obvious discrimination. On the economic

front, there is huge disparity between the quality of education (including access to technology) from one school to another, both within states and nationwide.

The problem is that education can often afford to take its own sweet time about things, without fear of failure, without fear of losing students. Sometimes, even, schools gain cachet by being snootily anachronistic. "We don't use computers here. We believe education should be done the old-fashioned way." In India, the sense I have is that the state of technology-integrated teaching and learning is much like it was in the United States in the mid-80s. There is a lot of hype. A token number of computers are being purchased and installed in many schools at all levels. Training programs have been initiated for teachers, again at all levels. But certain key requirements for successful implementation are lacking.

- Teacher-training in the practical use of computerbased technologies is sporadic and far from ongoing. Indeed, there are but two government sponsored e- Learning centers for training teachers to integrate technology into the primary and secondary school curriculum nationwide.
- There are only a few computers (5-20) in those schools that have them. Hardly any students have computers for individual use, whether at school or at home.
- Where there are computers, they are often not connected to the internet. Where they are connected to the internet, the connection speed is slow.
- Almost invariably, the computers are clustered in a computer lab, to which students go for instruction in how to use them. They learn the basics. They do not have the opportunity to use the computers on a regular basis to advance their skills. Nor are the computers integrated into learning

across the curriculum. The state of technology integrated teaching and learning in India is nascent at best, notwithstanding a token introduction of computers in some of the schools. There are exceptions, so-called "Center Universities," such as the Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs) and other well-endowed schools, which are showcase universities funded by the federal government of India, one per state, and designed specifically to attract and train a technology-skilled workforce for the burgeoning high tech industry that is making India such an attractive place to do business.

Conclusion

Technology-integrated education is still a dream at all levels of education in India. While there are computers in the schools, they are mostly used to learn about computers. Rarely are they used as tools for the teaching and learning of other curriculum areas yet. But there is an advantage to India's being behind the times, as long as the leaders in education keep their wits about them. They can skip wire-based technologies altogether. Wi-MAX, the latest generation broadband wireless medium, will be made available everywhere; it's just a matter of time. Computers, too, continue to come down in price. This will enable schools to connect to the internet at speeds that will make internet use, inside and outside the classroom, a viable adjunct to chalk and talk and traditional textbook learning an adjunct, not an alternative. Traditional learning methodologies will continue to have an important place in education. Students who routinely use the computer for learning do so because they have come to value it as a tool for accessing and processing information, for communicating and collaborating, for building a community of learners in which ideas are shared, and for increasing their

awareness of the world of knowledge to which they can gain access at the touch of their fingertips. Those who are lucky enough to have the computer as part and parcel of their academic experience would never be without it. The opportunity to use computers for teaching and learning should not be a privilege. It should be a right, just as it is only right that children should have access to books, pens and paper. There is a digital divide that separates the haves and have-nots with regard to access to technology. It is only right that the privilege of technology-integrated teaching and learning should be enjoyed by all.

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